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Roman archaeology of the Lower Danube region, spoke on the evidence for Trajan's conquest of Dacia (the area of modern Romania). Concentrating on the Roman army and the evidence from the iconography of the sculptured frieze around Trajan's Column and other sources, he also illustrated his lecture with a practical demonstration of Roman armour. The final lecture was given by Dr Nicholas Hodgson (Arbeia Roman Fort and Museum, Keeper of Archaeology and Principal Officer of Collections and Research at Tyne and Wear Archives and Museums) one of our leading scholars on Roman military archaeology in the north of Britain and well known to many delegates for his ARA study tours of Hadrian's Wall, the Antonine Wall and Roman Scotland. He spoke on *Britannia Omissa* – the military situation in Britain under Trajan.

The papers by Drs Bernhard Woytek and Nicholas Hodgson are included here as Part I of the proceedings of the Symposium.

Fig. 3: Monumental portrait head of Trajan found near the Theatre in Ostia in 1913, Hadrianic, made of Greek Luna marble probably by a Greek artist. Ostia Museum, inv. 17.

Photo: © Grahame Soffe.

However, due to illness after the Symposium, Professors Amanda Claridge and Andrew Poulter were unable to submit their papers in publishable form and so it was decided by the editorial board of ARA with the speakers' consent to reconstruct these contributions from audio recordings made at the Symposium and other original sources and publish these together with Prof. John Wilkes's closing remarks as Part II of the Symposium's proceedings in the next issue of ARA. As many readers will know, Amanda Claridge became seriously ill and died on 5 May 2022 and Andrew Poulter died on 30 November 2025, a great shock and enormous loss to Roman archaeology.

**SPQR OPTIMO PRINCIPI
Trajanic Coinage as a
Tribute to “the Best of
Emperors”**

*by Bernhard Woytek (Austrian
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The imperial coinage of Trajan certainly is among the most complex and fascinating of the Roman principate – for many different reasons: for example, Trajan's coins are well-known for the depiction of several famous buildings and monuments in Rome. Also, they illustrate a few key events of Trajan's reign, through a detailed representation of historical scenes, which are shown in a strikingly innovative way. Furthermore, a special phenomenon has been attracting scholarly interest for centuries: Trajan restored dozens of older Roman coin types, in gold and silver. I would like to introduce the readers to some of these aspects of Trajan's coins, the golden thread being the emperor's name or, more precisely, the way Trajan is referred to in the inscriptions of his coins.

Let us start with a gold coin (*aureus*) of Trajan, struck at the mint of Rome around ten years into Trajan's reign (Fig. 5). On the

Fig. 4: Sardonyx cameo depicting jugate portraits of Trajan laureate and his wife Plotina whose hair is arranged in thick masses of plaits over her forehead. 50 by 43mm. BM no, 1824,0301.97.GR.

Photo: © The Trustees of the British Museum.

obverse, the emperor is depicted as a general, in military attire, wearing a cuirass and a cloak, the so-called *paludamentum*. The legend in the round gives his name and some of his titles; it is in the dative case. IMP(eratori) TRAIANO AVG(usto) GER(manico) DAC(ico) P(ontifici) M(aximo) TR(ibunicia) P(otestate) CO(n)S(uli) V P(atri) P(atriae): “to the Emperor Traianus Augustus Germanicus Dacicus, to the High Priest, who holds the tribunician power, Consul for the fifth time, Father of the Fatherland.”

On the reverse, there is a wreath made of oak leaves, and a dedicatory inscription: S(enatus) P(opulus)Q(ue) R(omanus) OPTIMO PRINCIPI – “the senate and people of Rome to the best of emperors”. This reverse image stands in a typological tradition harking back to the very beginning of the principate: the oak wreath is the *corona civica*, originally during the Republic a military decoration awarded to a Roman soldier who had saved a fellow-citizen’s life. Under the empire its meaning was transformed. In 27 BC, the *corona civica* was awarded to Augustus by the Senate, as a token of gratitude for saving the Roman state from the terrors of the Civil Wars and for “transferring the *res publica* from his own control back to the senate and the people” to use the official wording preserved in the *Res gestae* of Augustus (RgdA 34.1–2). The crown was

widely publicised on Augustan coins, and it was traditionally accompanied by the words OB CIVIS SERVATOS (“for saving the citizens”). After Augustus, a typological tradition developed. His successors used the *corona civica* as an imperial insignia that was not only displayed above the entrance of the imperial palace, (Suet. Claud. 17: *atque inter hostilia spolia navalem coronam fastigio Palatinae domus iuxta civicam fixit*) but also repeatedly depicted on coins, for example under Caligula, Claudius, or Vespasian (Fig. 6). The inscriptions at the centre of the wreath then traditionally contained an abbreviated version of the legend “the senate and people of Rome” (or “by a decree of the senate”) “to the Father of the Fatherland for saving the citizens”. This provides the context for the reverse of our *aureus* of Trajan, featuring the *corona civica* and the dedication “to the best of emperors”.

But the use of the formula SPQR OPTIMO PRINCIPI is by no means limited to the Trajanic coin types with *corona civica*: it occurs extremely often on the reverses of Trajan’s imperial coins, whatever they depict. For example, from AD 113 onwards series of coins featuring Trajan’s column were issued in all three metals. This image was not accompanied by a specific descriptive legend, though, but originally by the text “The senate and people of Rome to

the best of emperors” (Fig. 7) – and the same is true for dozens and dozens of other reverse types. It needs to be stressed, however, that this legend was not used from the beginning of Trajan’s principate: during the first five to six years, the formulation of coin inscriptions entirely conformed to the practice of some earlier reigns: the legends are in the nominative case, and they give the name and titles of the emperor, normally extending over both sides of the coins. Thus, on a *sestertius* of early AD 103, depicting the emperor and Roma on the reverse (Fig. 8), the legend says: IMP(erator) CAES(ar) NERVA TRAIAN(us) AVG(ustus) GERM(anicus) DACICVS P(ontifex) M(aximus) – TR(ibunicia) P(otestate) VII IMP(erator) IIII CO(n)S(ul) V P(ater) P(atriae).

This first phase of Trajanic coinage, in which the behaviour of the coin inscriptions is inconspicuous, and firmly traditional, extends up to the aftermath of the First Dacian War: in the autumn of AD 102, Trajan returned victorious from the campaign, and held his first triumph on one of the last days of the year; on January 1st AD 103 he entered upon his fifth consulship.

A few months into the year 103, there was the great paradigm shift in coinage, and the mint proceeded to a complete reshuffle of the structures of the legends.

Left to right:

Fig. 5: Trajan, *aureus*, mint of Rome, c. AD 107. Woytek 2010, no. 224f. 7.37g, die-axis 6h, diameter 19mm. Classical Numismatic Group Triton 22 (8 January 2019), no. 1064.

Fig. 6: Caligula, *sestertius*, mint of Rome, AD 37/38. RIC Gaius 37. 28.23g, diameter 36mm. Numismatica Ars Classica 114 (6 May 2019), no. 605.

Photo: © CNG.

Photo: © NAC.

Left to right:

Fig. 7: Trajan, aureus, mint of Rome, c. AD 113. Woytek 2010, no. 424f. 7.06g; die-axis 6h, diameter 19mm. Museo Archeologico di Firenze, inv. no. 35713/226.

Photo: © Fiorenzo Catalli.

Fig. 8: Trajan, sestertius, mint of Rome, AD 103. Woytek 2010, no. 158b. 27.21g, diameter 34mm. Gorny & Mosch Giessener Münzhandlung 175 (9 March 2009), no. 246.

Photo: © Gorny & Mosch.

— The obverse legends are no longer in the nominative case, but in the dative case. While they originally indicated who was responsible for striking the coins, they now become a ‘dedication’ to the emperor.

— On the reverse, we find, from 103 onwards, in most cases the fixed formula SPQR OPTIMO PRINCIPI.

It is at least in a certain way still possible to read the legends continuously from the obverse to the reverse of the coins: “to the Emperor Caesar Nerva Traianus” etc. “the senate and people of Rome to the best of emperors”. However, the legends of the two sides also work independently of each other.

How do we know that this paradigm shift is to be dated to AD 103, although we have no indication of the *tribunicia potestas* on coins with these legends? There are various clues to the correct dating, one of them being a *sestertius* type of the first SPQR OPTIMO PRINCIPI group documenting Trajan’s building activities at the *Circus Maximus* in Rome (Fig. 9): the emperor enlarged its capacity by 5000 places and re-built the colonnaded wing of the circus prominently shown in the foreground of the reverse (Pliny, *Panegyric* 51.3). There is epigraphic evidence for the works: the inscription commemorating the dedication of the new wing (CIL VI 955 = ILS 286) is dated to AD 103 (before

December 10th). We may expect this coin type to have been issued around the time when the works were completed. One of the arguments to that effect is the parallel of the coins featuring the column of Trajan, mentioned above: the earliest of them were produced precisely in AD 113, when the monument was inaugurated. Hence, the *sestertii* with the Circus confirm that the re-shuffle concerning the Trajanic legends took place in the year AD 103.

The new slogan SPQR OPTIMO PRINCIPI was used on Trajan’s imperial coinage from AD 103 to 114, and some crude statistics may help to demonstrate how pervasive it was. In the current standard reference for Trajan’s imperial coinage (Woytek 2010), 618 coin types struck in Trajan’s name featuring his portrait on the obverse are listed; of these around 220 bear this catchphrase, and further 52 an abbreviated version of it, viz. SPQR OPTIMO PRINC. This means that about 44% of Trajan’s imperial coin types display this reverse legend, in one form or the other. Keeping in mind that not all coin types were struck in equal numbers, of course, and that many of the coin types with this new slogan are among the most common Trajanic types that we know, it is safe to assume that altogether more than 50% of Trajan’s coins feature the phrase SPQR OPTIMO PRINC (or PRINCIPI). In other words, if you randomly pick up a coin of Trajan,

chances are that it has this legend. It is Trajan’s numismatic trademark *par excellence*. This standardisation is something previously unheard of, in Roman imperial times, and Trajan is almost a precursor of Late Antiquity here, when standardised reverse legends like GENIO POPVLI ROMANI, GLORIA EXERCITVS or FEL(icium) TEMP(orum) REPARATIO were becoming the norm.

This new formula in the dative case takes the shape of a dedication to the ruler, which is to some extent against the tradition of inscriptions on ancient coins. Coin legends were mostly in the genitive or in the nominative case, as an answer to the imaginary questions: Whose coin is it? Who had it made? Who guarantees for its value?

So, what was it that was dedicated to Trajan? The formula must surely be understood as referring either to the coin it is stamped upon, or to the images that are accompanied by the formula. This observation leads us to a hotly debated theory regarding Roman imperial coin types. In a classic article published in 1982, Barbara Levick argued against the traditional interpretation of Roman coin designs as “propaganda” directed towards the coin users, and took an alternative view: “The types were intended to appeal, not to the public, but to the man whose

Left to right:

Fig. 9: Trajan, *sestertius*, mint of Rome, c. AD 103. Woytek 2010, no. 175a. 25.8g, diameter 35mm. *Numismatica Ars Classica* 97 (12 December 2016), no. 111. Photo: © NAC.

Fig. 10: Trajan, *aureus*, mint of Rome, c. AD 113/114. Woytek 2010, no. 418f–3. 7.27g, diameter 20mm. *Numismatica Ars Classica* 99 (29 May 2017), no. 7. Photo: © NAC.

portrait as a rule occupied the obverse of the coins: they were a public tribute to a great individual” (Levick 1982, 107). Of course, this *a priori* ties in well with a dedicatory dative in the coin inscriptions.

According to the traditional explanatory model, the mint and the emperor sent messages to the public, through the coins; it is assumed that the creation of types normally followed an exchange between the ruler (or his inner circle) and the designers at the mint, who were checking what was desired by the court. According to Levick’s theory, by contrast, the mint primarily communicated with the emperor on the coinage. There certainly is a germ of truth in this, but I would submit that it is not the whole truth. The slogan SPQR OPTIMO PRINCIPI is of course *prima facie* directed exclusively towards the emperor,

but by disseminating it on an empire-wide basis, in incredibly large numbers, and by hammering this phrase into the heads of the coin-users (at least of those who could read), the mint created an atmosphere of veneration; also, these words may have been intended to foster the loyalty of the people towards the emperor. The reduction of reverse legends in favour of this one slogan is remarkable, and it seems to invite us to draw a parallel to strategies of brand recognition in modern advertising: you just have to repeat your message and the name of your product often enough.

Thus, I suggest that the phrase SPQR OPTIMO PRINCIPI is to be understood as geared both towards Trajan and his subjects. The traditional explanation of the mechanisms involved in Roman numismatic mass-communication must not be discarded entirely.

In any case, the catchphrase was so common on coins of Trajan that it frequently turns up on later coin types copied from his issues. Let me give just one example here: the legionary eagle between standards is one of the classic military types of Trajan. It is based on earlier prototypes, of course, but was popular at the mint of Rome especially in the years 112–114, when this emperor prepared his ominous campaign against the Arsacid state: during those years it was used on *aurei* (Fig. 10) and *denarii*. Constantine the Great, who was an avid admirer of Trajan, not only had some of his portraits modelled on Trajanic portrait types, but also took up some of Trajan’s coin types (A special study on this phenomenon is currently being prepared by this author). A good example is the copy of the typical Trajanic image of legionary eagle and standards, together with the slogan SPQR

Left to right:

Fig. 11: Constantine I, the Great, *solidus*, mint of Trier, c. AD 310–313. RIC 6, Treveri 815.4.53g, diameter 18mm. Gorny & Mosch Giessener Münzhandlung 159 (8 October 2007), no. 474. Photo: © Gorny & Mosch.

Fig. 12: Trajan, *sestertius*, mint of Rome, c. AD 114–116. Woytek 2010, no. 551v (no SC in reverse legend). 26.51g, diameter 34mm. Reverse slightly double-struck. *Numismatica Ars Classica* 59 (4 April 2011), no. 982. Photo: © NAC.

OPTIMO PRINCIPI, on a type of Constantine's gold *solidi* (Fig. 11).

The appellation “*optimus princeps*” was used from AD 103 onwards for more than ten years. Its appearance on coins indicates that this was official usage – still, “*optimus*” was not part of Trajan’s name, then: it is found just on the reverse of his coins, as part of the omnipresent catchphrase.

However, this was to change during Trajan’s fateful eastern campaign against the Parthians. Trajan left Rome in the late summer of AD 113 and relocated the imperial court to Antioch on the Orontes for the next four years – this is, by the way, another point that makes Trajan appear as a precursor of later, third- and fourth-century developments. The first military action of the following year 114 was directed towards Armenia, where the Arsacid king of kings had enthroned a vassal as the new ruler without asking for Rome’s permission, a certain Parthamasiris, an Arsacid prince. In Elegeia, in Armenia, Trajan received the Parthian king of Armenia in the Roman camp, and Parthamasiris submitted to the Roman emperor – in the hope that Trajan might confirm his appointment. But Trajan would not dream of doing this, annexed Armenia as a Roman province instead and put poor Parthamasiris to death.

When news of the annexation of Armenia reached Rome in the spring of AD 114, the senate officially expanded Trajan’s titulature by adding the name OPTIMVS. This name appears in the obverse legend of an extremely rare *sestertius* type struck at the mint of Rome, commemorating the scene in the Roman camp at Elegeia (Fig. 12): IMP(eratori) CAES(ari) NER(vae) TRAIANO OPTIMO AVG(usto) etc. The reverse image of the piece is very detailed and may be analysed against the background of a colourful description of the event by Cassius Dio (68.19 20): Trajan

Fig. 13: Trajan, *aureus*, mint of Rome, AD 114. Woytek 2010, no. 497f. 7.07g, die-axis 6h, diameter 20mm. Royal Library Brussels, Coin Cabinet, inv. II, 62.768. Photo: © author.

is seated to the left on a podium, with an attendant behind him, and a lictor standing next to the podium; opposite the emperor there are Roman soldiers with military standards, and the bearded Parthian king of Armenia is shown during the act of submission. He is identified as REX PARTHVS because he was of Arsacid descent. This image also serves to illustrate another main feature of Trajanic coinage in general group scenes. Under Trajan, there is a close correspondence between numismatic and monumental art. His reign marks the heyday of state relief, whether we think of Trajan’s column, the great Trajanic frieze, or the arch of *Beneventum*. On the imperial coinage of this period, we suddenly find ‘miniature reliefs’, group scenes comprising up to ten people, as in this case. This is an

innovation for Roman coinage, clearly related to artistic developments in state relief (see Wolfram Thill 2014).

When Armenia was annexed, Trajan received his seventh imperial acclamation. It was the first salutation of the Parthian campaign, and the first imperial acclamation ever to be depicted on Roman coins – on a rare *aureus* type of AD 114 (Fig. 13). Again, a crowded scene, in this case on a coin with a diameter of less than two centimetres: Trajan on the podium, here accompanied by two attendants; one *lictor* in front of the platform, six soldiers standing facing and acclaiming him, standards in the background, and even one horse in the middle of the crowd. Trajan is already called Optimus in the obverse legend here as well.

Fig. 14: Trajan, restored *denarius*, mint of Rome, c. AD 112/113. Woytek 2010, no. 804. 3.31g, die-axis 6h, diameter 19mm. Staatliche Museen zu Berlin, Münzkabinett, object no.18207119. <<https://ikmk.smb.museum/object?id=18207119>>(9 November 2019). Photo: © Staatliche Museen zu Berlin.

Fig. 15: Relative frequency of the terms *optimus* and *dominus* in honorific inscriptions for the emperor, expressed as a percentage of all honorific terms (based on 575 inscriptions). From Noreña 2011, 285, figure 5.3. © Carlos F. Noreña.

The change to Trajan's name in AD 114 made structural modifications of his coin legends necessary. After the element "Optimus" had been integrated into Trajan's name on the obverse, keeping "SPQR OPTIMO PRINCIPI" (*vel sim.*) on the reverse would have been repetitive: hence, the adoption of "Optimus" as part of Trajan's name made the classic formula on the reverse redundant. However, the mint found an elegant solution to the problem. They kept the emperor's name on the obverse in the dative case and left out "OPTIMO PRINCIPI" on the reverse. The inscription of the coins continued to be a dedication, but the obverse and reverse needed to be understood together, so that the reader got the full message: on precious metal coins, the titulature was allowed to spill over onto the reverse, where the legend ended in SPQR; on the larger base metal coins, the titulature remained confined to the obverse, while SPQR was

simply expanded to SENATVS POPVLVSQVE ROMANVS, in order to fill the empty space. This basic structure of legends was retained for the final three years of Trajan's reign in his coinage.

We have seen that *optimus* was used on Trajan's coins first as a mere epithet, and from AD 114 onwards as a real name, but what is its deeper meaning? The word is the superlative of the adjective *bonus* ("good"), and several studies by Joseph Vogt (1933) and Barbara Scardigli (1974) have elucidated the political background of this name or title, its connection with the Republican concept of the "vir bonus" and with the Greek aristocratic role model of the "ἄριστος ἀνὴρ". They have shown that the name also has important philosophical undertones, and that it primarily refers to the moral excellence of a ruler. The Trajanic inner circle insisted on the fact that a Roman emperor had to be a model for the senators and all Romans. It is important to interpret this against the backdrop of the controversial reign of the last Flavian, Domitian, that had ended just one and a half years before Trajan acceded to the throne.

Two passages in the Panegyric of Pliny the Younger may serve to illustrate the connotations that the name had to contemporaries, especially to senators. Pliny says: "Nobody can appear to be '*optimus*' if he does not surpass all the other '*optimi*' in the fields of their respective excellence" (*nec videri potest optimus, nisi qui est optimis omnibus in sua cuiusque laude praestantior*, §88). This means, Trajan has higher moral qualities than all the others in whatever field. And Pliny also remarks that "the senators do not need orders so much as an example. Fear is an unreliable teacher of what is right: men learn better from examples" (*nec tam imperio nobis opus est quam exemplo, quippe infidelis recti magister est metus. melius homines exemplis docentur*, §45). This is, unsurprisingly, another reference to Domitian – the Panegyric is full of them. Domitian seems to have created a climate of fear and anxiety through which the senate was kept in check; and Pliny here contrasts Trajan's style of leadership with Domitian's.

Trajan was presented as a role model for all Romans. But at the same time, the emperor's inner circle was keen on defining the emperor's place in Roman history. A group of numismatic sources is crucial for understanding the preoccupation of the Trajanic government with the relationship to the past: the so-called restored coins. The coin in Figure 14 is a good example. It is a *denarius* of a type originally struck at the mint of Rome around 120 BC by a Republican moneyer called M. Tullius, featuring the traditional helmeted head of Roma on the obverse and Victory in a *biga* on the reverse. Under Trajan this coin type was re-issued, around 230 years after its original appearance. The *denarius* faithfully reproduces the Republican legends and designs, and just an additional legend on the reverse discloses the new minting authority: IMP(erator) CAES(ar)TRAIANVS AVG(ustus)

Fig. 16: Trajan, *denarius*, mint of Rome, c. January/February AD 98. Woytek 2010, no. 10a. 3.53g, die-axis 7h, diameter 17mm. Roma Numismatics E-Sale 57 (30 May 2019), no. 878. Photo: © Roma Numismatics.

GER(manicus)DAC(icus) P(ater) P(atriciae)REST(ituit). Trajan “restored” the coin type of the moneyer M. Tullius.

Around fifty Republican *denarius* types were re-issued in this way, but also imperial *aurei*, mainly of the ‘good emperors’ from Julius Caesar to Vespasian, Titus and Trajan’s predecessor Nerva. As for the principles that governed the choice of the Republican types to be restored, various factors may have played a part. Attractiveness of the designs aside, it seems clear that the names on the original issues mattered, too: there seems to have been some attempt to produce an overview of famous Romans in coinage – for example, the *denarius* issue produced by Caesar’s assassin M. Iunius Brutus as a moneyer was restored. The large series of restored coins of Trajan, to be dated to AD 112/113, puts Trajan in the context of Rome’s glorious past, from the Republican beginnings to the Principate, and marks Trajan’s rule as the culmination of Roman history. He was the *optimus princeps*, who outdid all the past emperors in his ruler qualities.

In a monograph published a few years ago, Carlos Noreña studied the occurrence of the epithet *optimus* in the Latin epigraphic evidence: in honorific inscriptions for emperors, to be precise, from the Flavian period to the third century (Noreña 2011, 283–97). He took into account not only official inscriptions of the highest level, but also municipal inscriptions and dedications set up by private individuals or associations, so that ‘non-official’ usage of titles is covered as well. There are two curves in his diagram (Fig. 15): the thin line charts the occurrence of *optimus*, and the thicker one that of the epithet *dominus*. The chart shows that the epithet *optimus* occurred in inscriptions mainly between Domitian and Commodus, the most important period being the time-frame from Trajan to Marcus

Aurelius, as we would expect. Subsequently, it was superseded by the name *dominus* in inscriptions, which seems significant. However, the diagram also illustrates that the epithet *optimus*, popularised by Trajan, continued in unofficial use for most of the second century and beyond, although Trajan was the only emperor of this period who used it in his official titulature.

Noreña’s monograph was published in 2011. In the very same year, an exciting inscription was discovered in the Italian city of Brescia; it was published three years later (Gregori 2014). It is an honorary inscription in Prokonnesian marble, the letters of which are not only carved into the stone, but also painted in red. It was set up for Caligula in AD 41, at the end of his rule, by a priestess of Diva Drusilla. The wording of the inscription is spectacular; its first four lines run as follows:

[Pro s]alute et reditu et victor(ia)
[C. Caesa]ris Aug(usti) principis
optimi
[pontif(ici)s] max(imi) pron(epotis)
divi Aug(usti) trib(unicia)
[potest(ate) IIII] co(n)s(ulis)
desig(nati) V imp(eratoris) [VI]I
p(atris) p(atriciae) p(atris)
exercit(uum)

This inscription proves that Caligula was called “*princeps optimus*” already a generation

before Noreña’s period of investigation starts. Also, he bears the surprising epithet of *pater exercituum* (“father of the armies”) in this inscription. Hence, the dedication largely confirms a statement made by Suetonius, in the life of Caligula (22.1), according to which this emperor was called “*pater exercituum et optimus maximus Caesar*”, among other things – a statement often dismissed prior to the discovery of this inscription. To be clear: *optimus* was not part of Caligula’s official titulature, unlike in the case of Trajan. Still, it is an important precedent, and it shows that something was in the air, already long before Trajan.

This leaves us with the all-important question of why the concept of *optimus princeps* was transferred from the unofficial to the official sphere precisely under Trajan? I believe that a plausible answer is to be sought in the circumstances of the emperor’s accession. As is well known, Trajan was adopted by Nerva in the autumn of AD 97. He was *legatus Augusti pro praetore* of Upper Germany at that time, so that he had to be adopted *in absentia*, and Trajan remained at the northern frontier of the empire for almost two years, after his sole rule had started in January AD 98. A *denarius* type that was used exclusively in the very first issue of Trajan’s reign features the adoption (Fig. 16). It shows Trajan

Fig. 17: Trajan, *aureus*, mint of Rome, c. AD 112/113. Woytek 2010, no. 400f. 7.28g, die-axis 7h, diameter 19mm. Paris, Bibliothèque nationale de France. Ancien Fonds no. 588.

Photo: © author.

in military dress, and Nerva in the *toga*: Nerva seems to pass on a globe to Trajan. In the exergue, the letters PROVID, standing for *providentia*, praise Nerva's foresight in adopting Trajan. This reverse type was, however, used only in the first few weeks of Trajan's reign in January/February AD 98.

Then, apparently at the moment when instructions from Trajan (who was in Germany) arrived in Rome, production of this type was discontinued, and for the following 14 years there was no numismatic commemoration of Nerva whatsoever. Trajan did keep the name "Nerva", which he had inherited from his adoptive father, but he relegated it from second to third spot in his imperial name: "Imperator Caesar Nerva...", no longer "Imperator Nerva Caesar", as in his earliest issue, which the PROVID *denarii* were part of. Nerva was immediately deified, to be sure, but the Divus Nerva was not featured on any imperial coins of Trajan for more than ten years. Numismatically speaking, Trajan in this period almost pretended that his adoptive father Nerva did not exist (see Woytek 2017).

Nerva's portrait was depicted for the first time only in AD 112/113, at the eve of the Parthian campaign, but not on his own: by that point in time, Trajan had deified his natural father, too, as Divus Traianus Pater, and therefore could boast two fathers who were gods. This was the occasion for the production of splendid gold coins with the portraits of both of his fathers on the reverse (Fig. 17). In the regular issues, Nerva's portrait was never featured on his own on one side of a Trajanic coin; it only occurs on extremely rare *aurei* of the restored series (Woytek 2010, nos 872–3 and 877[H]).

The reason for this neglect was that Nerva was not perceived to be a worthy father for the new emperor: his short reign was a troubled one. Nerva was an old

senator, of frail health. In AD 97, he had to deal with a dangerous revolt of the praetorian guard, who forced him to turn in the murderers of Domitian – the last Flavian was held in high regard by the military, not least because he had granted the soldiers a substantial pay-rise. From this point onwards, Nerva was without his most trusted friends, and he was an emperor with a "date of expiry", so to speak. Modern historical research has made it clear that he did not act out of his own free will, when he adopted Trajan, but that he was most probably forced to do so by an influential group of senators, around Sex. Iulius Frontinus and L. Iulius Ursus. They were successful in establishing their preferred candidate on the throne, against the praetorian guard. Consequently, Nerva was far from being the best ideological point of reference for Trajan. Could an invincible warrior-prince possibly descend from a weak old senator, who was hardly more than a placeholder on the throne? Of course not. For this reason, Trajan and his advisers came up with a spectacular and innovative solution. As we read in Pliny's Panegyric, they pretended that Nerva in adopting Trajan merely obeyed the will of the gods, in particular of Jupiter Optimus Maximus. In paragraph 8 of the speech Pliny literally says: *Nerva tantum minister fuit* – Nerva was just a servant, a "minister of Jupiter", who executed the

command of the supreme god in choosing Trajan as his successor.

Hence, Trajan's ideological point of reference was not so much Nerva, who was just an instrument that the gods had used for bringing Trajan onto the throne – the decisive point of reference was Jupiter himself, Rome's highest god. We have to take this into account in interpreting (inofficial) epigraphic documents in which Trajan is not only styled *optimus princeps*, but *optimus maximus princeps*: *Ex indulgentia optimi maxime principis imp(eratoris) Caes(aris) Nervae Traiani Aug(usti)...* (AD 107–114: CIL XI 1147); *optimo maximo(ue) principi imp(eratori) Nervae Traian(o) Caesari Aug(usto)...* (AD 112/113: AE 1993, 472f.); *optimo maximoque principi conservatori generis humani* (AD 118: CIL II 2054). This clearly echoes the name of Jupiter Optimus Maximus: Trajan was an emperor surrounded by a divine aura.

The ideology created by Trajan and his inner circle represents a momentous paradigm shift in Roman imperial history. It finds its most important numismatic expression in a coin type that was struck in gold, silver and bronze, in AD 113/114 (for the *aureus*, see Fig. 18): Trajan, the emperor, is shown under Jupiter's cloak, under the god's protection, and looking up to him. The god is much bigger than the emperor in this image – the hierarchical

Fig. 18: Trajan, *aureus*, mint of Rome, c. AD 112/113. Woytek 2010, no. 428f–1. 7.13 g, die-axis 7h, diameter 20mm. Staatliche Museen zu Berlin, Münzkabinett. Photo: © author.

proportion is observed. The type is accompanied by the legend CONSERVATORI PATRIS PATRIAE: “to the protector of the Father of the Fatherland”.

From Trajan onward, the religious aspect of Roman emperorship became decidedly more important than it was before. The concept reminds of the Christian ideology of the “divine right of kings”, or “Gottesgnadentum” of the Middle Ages and the Early Modern period. Trajan ruled over the Roman empire not because Nerva had adopted him, or because he was the best qualified candidate. He ruled because Jupiter had commanded it: Trajan was on a divine mission.

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Bibliography

Gregori, G. L., 2014, Un’ eccezionale dedica a favore di Caligola, in: F. Rossi (ed.), *Un luogo per gli dei. L’area del Capitolium a Brescia*, Florence, 303–6.

Levick, B., 1982, Propaganda and the imperial coinage, *Antichthon* 16, 104–16.

Noreña, C. F., 2011, *Imperial Ideals in the Roman West. Representation, Circulation, Power*, Cambridge. RIC: see Sutherland 1967 and 1984.

Scardigli, B., 1974, *Da Traianus Optimus Princeps a Traianus Optimus Augustus, Quaderni Urbinati di Cultura Classica* 18, 57–103.

Sutherland, C. H. V., 1967, *The Roman Imperial Coinage*, vol. 6: *From Diocletian’s reform (A.D. 294) to the death of Maximinus (A.D. 313)*, London.

Sutherland, C. H. V., 1984, *The Roman Imperial Coinage*, vol.1, *second edition: From 31 BC to AD 69*, London.

Vogt, J., 1933, Vorläufer des Optimus Princeps, *Hermes* 68, 84–92.

Wolfram Thill, E., 2014, The Emperor in Action: Group Scenes in Trajanic Coins and Monumental Reliefs, *American Journal of Numismatics (second series)* 26, 87–140.

Woytek, B., 2010, *Die Reichsprägung des Kaisers Traianus*, 2 vols, Vienna.

Woytek, B., 2017, Divus Nerva. The coin evidence, in: L. Bricault, A.

Burnett, V. Drost and A. Suspène (eds), *Rome et les provinces. Monnayage et histoire. Mélanges offerts à Michel Amandry*, Bordeaux, 195–212.

Britannia Omissa: the military situation in Britain under Trajan

by Nick Hodgson

A generation separates two of the most famously documented and intensively studied episodes in Roman military affairs in Britain. These are: the invasion of Scotland under Agricola, his victory at Mons Graupius (83) followed by the planting, and then immediate abandonment (by 87) of a legionary presence in the far north; and the visit of Hadrian in 122 and the building of his Wall across the Tyne Solway Isthmus. The intervening period is 35 years and the distance between the northernmost known fort in Scotland and Hadrian’s Wall is 125 miles. How and why did this spectacular fall-back, so critical to understanding the build-up to Hadrian’s Wall, taken place?

To find the answer we need to see what was going on in the reign of the emperor Trajan, which takes up much of the time (98–117). But this is not an easy thing to do, for a simple reason: there is not a single surviving ancient historical source which mentions any event, military or otherwise, in Britain for the whole of Trajan’s reign.

In the absence of any literary guideposts – and near absence of stone inscriptions, for most military building was still in turf and timber – knowledge of the

Fig. 19. Map of the Trajanic frontier on the Stanegate between the Solway and the Tyne.

Courtesy of *Frontiers of the Roman Empire Culture 2000 Project*/D.J. Breeze.